

CYBERBULLYING TWEET CLASSIFICATION USING LANGUAGE MODELS

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ABSTRACT

Cyberbullying is a severe problem in the age of social media and round-the-clock connectivity. Detecting cyberbullying is the first step in the right direction to enhancing online safety and improving mental health. Some organizations have a legal and ethical responsibility to carry out this task proactively to prevent harm to their employees or users. There is a lot of research on sentiment analysis in the realm of Natural Language Processing. However, for detecting and flagging cyberbullying, there are very few datasets out there (unlike toxicity detection or hate detection). In this paper, we explore the problem of cyberbullying tweet detection by approaching this as a classification problem. By leveraging the power of finetuning large language models (like LLAMA3 and Llama-Guard) using PEFT, we perform classification (after extracting the embeddings). We compare these techniques with traditional transformer-like approaches (SBERT). These conventional approaches have much smaller architectures than LLAMA3 and Llama-Guard. However, these models can help extract embeddings with power classification approaches such as Random Forests. The classification techniques we employ here show that the performance of LLAMA3 and Llama-Guard (trained with PEFT) compared to SBERT is more balanced.

Keywords: Classification, Language Models, Online Safety, Transformers, Natural Language Processing

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1. INTRODUCTION (12 BOLD)

Building online safety systems (inappropriate speech detection on hate speech, racism, bullying and bias, etc.) is a huge area of research. There is no dearth of problems to be explored in online safety systems in the realm of Natural Language Processing. Few of the problems include toxic text detection, hate speech detection, bias, racism, sexism and cyberbullying detection, etc. These problems have wide variety of applications in the online chatbots, social media, website content moderation. Sometimes, content moderation is required by law or regulations in some areas. These regulations help keep interactions between user groups safe and secure. To enforce such safety standards across all interactions between users/chatbots, intelligent NLP applications play a vital role. The content moderation systems form a vital part of strategy employed by several large organizations to keep users from harmful content generated by malicious users or bots. Such systems foster positive work/social environment, which is good for user mental health. These systems can be completely automated or partially automated (with human-in-the-loop). Such systems can be used to perform early detection, enforce legal compliance, uphold user safety and automatic moderation. The automated or human-in-the-loop system employ feature extraction techniques such as TF-IDF, BERT like embeddings, LLMs then use classification techniques such as Neural Networks, Logistic Regression or SoftMax Regression, Support Vector Machines, XGBoost or Random Forest classifiers to classify inputs into several cyberbullying classes. If the dataset contains multilingual content, one needs to switch to language agnostic features (such as LabSE, mBERT, XLM-RoBERTa, etc.). The embeddings are extracted from these models and passed to classification algorithms. Detecting and flagging cyberbullying is a major problem due to subtleties of language and context. These datasets are less widely available due to annotation challenges, ethical considerations and privacy concerns. This is unlike datasets that are widely available for detecting sentiment analysis (e.g. movies, new and product reviews, etc.). For this study, we focus our efforts in classifying the following 6 kinds of cyberbullying tweet classes: age, ethnicity, gender, religion, other cyberbullying and not cyberbullying. This dataset was obtained from Kaggle and is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 [1]. This dataset has around 47,692 tweets. This dataset was divided in train and test set of 35,769 and 11,923 respectively. There are roughly 7900 examples per class. A stratified split was performed on this dataset. This ensures that ratio of classes in train and test set are retained properly. That way the model is not skewed towards a certain class.

II. RELATED WORK

Building content moderation systems for social media (on user interactions) and e-commerce (reviews) has exponentially increased since the introduction of social media (and influencers). These systems are crucial parts of the pipeline that ensure users' safety and that organizations follow compliance procedures to continue staying in business. Such systems have been implemented from the ground up from the beginning of social media apps and websites. The first cyberbullying detection systems were based on text-related features (TF- IDF) and linear classifiers [2][3]. Other more straightforward approaches used were based on K-Nearest Neighbors [4][5], Support Vector Machine [2][4][5], and Decision Tree [5] that used text features such as Part of Speech tagging. Features such as Bag of Words, Character, and Word N-Grams were explored in [6]. These techniques were combined with classifiers such as SVM. Swear keyword indicator-based approaches were used in [7]. These were used along with TF-IDF-based approaches with an ensemble of one-class classifiers to perform cyberbullying detection. Feature engineering was a considerable focus before introducing automatic feature extraction based on Bidirectional encoder representations from transformers (BERT) and Language Models. BERT was trained on large English text datasets (books, Wikipedia).

Relatively modern pipelines are based on neural network-based classifiers on sentence encoder-based approaches (BERT, Universal Sentence Encoders, etc.). The BERT embeddings help understand nuances in human language and context. This makes it practical to extract representative features for the Cyberbullying Detection problem. Approaches explored in [8] include BERT-based approaches compared to SVM, CNN, etc. In the domain of cyberbullying detection, BERT-like embeddings were explored here [9][10]. Techniques based on these approaches are powerful as the models understand language nuance and context better than TF-IDF-based approaches (which are based on word frequency). Models trained on one dataset can be fine-tuned on other datasets if necessary. This avoids the hassle of using TF-IDF (essentially manual feature extraction), which may not be generalized to different domains (depending on the word frequencies). Features from these embeddings can be passed to neural networks, random forests (decision trees), and SoftMax layers to perform multi-class classification on huge datasets. In this study, we picked the BERT-based model provided by Google. SBERT is another popular model that we employed. SBERT models encode sentences into fixed-size embedding for semantic search in lower dimensional space [11]. This model was trained with PEFT [12], performing classification on a cyberbullying dataset. A BERT-like model is also considered a language model. These may be relatively smaller compared to larger language models such as GPT. A more recent phenomenon in the world of NLP includes the usage of Large Language Models to tackle cyberbullying detection [13][14]. Large Language Models (GPT3, LLAMA, LLAMA-GUARD, Mistral, etc.) have an inherent understanding of human language as they are trained with vast datasets of books, internet articles, and articles. They can be leveraged to understand nuances in cyberbullying detection. Our approaches focus primarily on LLAMA3, Llama-Guard. These models were shown to have impressive results on several language understanding tasks and safeguarding user inputs and model outputs, respectively. Llama-Guard is an LLM often used to flag unsafe content when users interact with bots. We picked these three models (LLAMA3, Llama-Guard, and SBERT) for this study.

III. OUR APPROACH

This section outlines our approach to classify the cyberbullying dataset into several classes. We cover more recent approaches (rather than TF-IDF-based hand-crafted features) like SBERT, LLAMA3, and Llama-Guard. We have used the SBERT model, which was chosen for its ability to encode text in lower dimensions. Similar sentences have similar-looking embeddings in lower dimensions. The SBERT model can help group text that is paraphrased (when projected into lower dimensions of 384). These features are passed to a Random Forest based classifier.

SBERT-like models are good at encoding similar sentences into lower-dimensional vector space (in this case, data was projected to a lower dimension of length 384). This model was trained on internet data such as Reddit comments, WikiAnswers, Stack Exchange, Yahoo Answers, Quora questions, etc.

The LLAMA3 (8B Instruct) model was trained on internet data. It was trained with 15 trillion tokens and over 10 million human annotated samples [15][16]. This widely used model often serves as an industry standard to tackle common NLP problems. The Llama-Guard (7B) model [17] used in this experiment includes a slightly older model based on LLAMA2. The Llama-Guard model can identify and flag NSFW (Not-Safe-For-Work) content. It is designed to perform prompt classification and response classification. It can identify content that includes *violence*, *hate*, *sexual content*, *hate speech*, and *self-harm*. These categories can be considered as widely overlapping with content in the cyberbullying dataset.

Figure 1: Data Distribution Pie Chart

The cyberbullying dataset split is mentioned in Figure 1. The dataset split per class is shown in Table 1. We performed a split of 75:25 of train and test sets (out of the total 47k samples). The split consisted of a stratified split to ensure the ratio of the train to test samples per class was retained. The LLAMA3 and Llama-Guard models were fine-tuned with the PEFT technique to improve performance on this dataset. The Llama-guard was only fine-tuned for one epoch as it can understand the content in our dataset. The LLAMA3 was trained with three epochs. The SBERT model wasn't trained further on this dataset. We extracted features from the SBERT model directly into 384-length feature vectors. These feature vectors were trained with a Random Forest classifier (with 100 estimators). The outline of this approach is highlighted in Figure 2. The training was performed on a NVIDIA A100 GPU. The SBERT model used for this study is a specific model called *paraphrase-MiniLM-L6-v2* [18] available on HuggingFace.

Figure 2: Model training and inference

Class	Count
religion	7998
age	7992
gender	7973
ethnicity	7961
Not cyberbullying	7945
Other cyberbullying	7823
Total	47692

Table 1: Class distribution count

IV. CONCLUSION

In this section, we discuss the performance of these models on train/ test sets and present the conclusion. The results from the train and test set are mentioned in Table 2 and Table 3, respectively. We can see that the SBERT model performed decently but tends to overfit. The Random Forest classifier is overfitting compared to LLM-based models such as LLAMA3 and Llama-guard. The LLM-based model performance on train and test is much more balanced than the results on SBERT. The LLM-based models without significant finetuning perform significantly better than the random forest models with SBERT embeddings.

Method	Precision	Recall	F1
SBERT	0.93	0.93	0.93
Llama-Guard (PEFT)	0.78	0.78	0.78
LLAMA3 (PEFT)	0.83	0.83	0.83

Table 2: Train set results

Method	Precision	Recall	F1
SBERT	0.73	0.73	0.73
Llama-Guard (PEFT)	0.77	0.77	0.77
LLAMA3 (PEFT)	0.80	0.80	0.80

Table 3: Test set results

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